

Aurora indicators for SDGs in OpenAIRE Monitor

AURORA

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Basics

- Important pages at this stage: Universities, Collaborations, Open Access
- Examples: <https://aurora-universities.eu/sdg-research/dashboard/>
- SDG Logo's & Color codes for non-un entities:
<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/news/communications-material/>
- Apply on: <https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/aurora>
- Embedding SDG-badges & API: <https://aurora-universities.eu/sdg-research/classify/>
- Re-using UN SDG ontology: <https://metadata.un.org/sdg>

Short term

- Filters
 - Per Aurora University (see <https://aurora.openaire.eu/organizations>)
 - Per SDG
 - Per Open Access color
 - Per co-authored affiliated country & aggregations by (sub)continent and development category.
 - Per field of science
- Overview
 - Donut chart: over laying the O in the logo for Sustainable development gOals
 - Ribbon charts(ranked by segment): Number and Percentage of Publications segmented by SDG, per year , in total for the whole monitor.
- Comparing Universities
 - Ribbon chart (rank per segment) / Stacked Bar Chart (stacks per segment)
 - Number and Percentage of Publications segmented by SDG, in total for the whole monitor.
 - Number and Percentage of Publications segmented by SDG, per year, in total for the whole monitor.
 - Number and Percentage of Publications segmented by SDG, per university (as defined in filter).
- Open Access
 - Horizontal Stacked bar chart (stacks by segment), number of publications for each Open Access color, segmented by SDGs.
 - Ribbon chart (ranked by Open Access color): Number and Percentage of Publications.
- Collaboration by publication co-authorship
 - World Map (auto zoom): heat map of publications per co-authored affiliated country
 - Ribbon chart (rank per category) / Stacked Bar Chart (segments per category)

- Top collaborating institutions: Number and Percentage of Publications segmented by SDG, of top 25 co-author affiliated universities (in total, not exclusively universities as defined in filter).
 - Top collaborating research fields: Number and Percentage of Publications segmented by SDG, of top 25 fields of science.
- Collaboration by grant project partners
 - Table heatmap (color graded cells): Aurora universities in columns, project partners (legal entities) in rows. In cells Count number of projects between aurora university and project partner.
 - Horizontal Stacked Bar chart (stacks per segment), number of publications for each project partner, segmented by SDGs

Long term

- Open Citations
- Mentions in policy documents, news, patents, blogs, social media.
- Aurora definitions of SDG labels

Appendix

Is it possible to add a “Collaboration” page to the “Project Grants” section?

<https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/aurora/research-output/project-grants>

What: We want to have a list of all project partners, Aurora universities work together with, by using the link between the publications (affiliated to aurora) and the projects. (see explanation below)

How: And if we have that connection, we want to filter on a specific SDG (or FoS), by using the publications as a proxy.

Why: Once we have that, we (our grant offices) can find past research collaborations done in these areas, for setting up new projects related to one of the SDG’s for example.

link between SDG publications and project partners

1. This SDG 2 (zero hunger) related publication is funded by an EC project

<https://aurora.openaire.eu/search/publication?pid=10.3389%2Fphys.2021.628236>

Which is related to one of the Aurora partners

Publication . Article . 2021

Usefulness of NGS for Diagnosis of Dominant Hemoglobinopathies in Five Clinical Cases

Valeria Rizzuto; Valeria Rizzuto; Valeria Rizzuto; Tamara T. Koopmann; Adora

Summary

Subjects

unstable hemoglobinopathies, dominant beta-thalassemia, next generation sequencing
Hemoglobinopatia, Seqüències d'inserció de l'ADN,...

Related Organizations

University of Barcelona

Spain

Leiden University Medical Center

Netherlands

Amsterdam UMC - Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

Netherlands

DNS

2. If we go to that EC project, we see that publicati on is one of 23, and that this project has several partners, public and private.

https://aurora.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::b9f7aa3beebdee3cd677759d2b7c350a

The screenshot shows the Aurora project page for 'EVIDENCE'. The project is titled 'EVIDENCE' and is described as 'Erythrocytes properties and viability in dependence of flow and extra-cellular environment'. It is an 'On going' project funded by the European Commission. The project code is 860436, and the call for proposal is H2020 MSCA-ITN-2019. The overall budget is 3,993,480 EUR, and the funder contribution is 3,993,480 EUR. The project started on 01 Jan 2020 and is set to end on 31 Dec 2023. The page includes a 'Summary' section with a description of the project's focus on red blood cells (RBCs) and their properties in flow conditions. A 'Partners' section lists various institutions including CNRS, EFS, Stichting Sanguin Bloedvoorziening, R6R, MECHATRONICS INTERNATIONAL BV, Erytech Pharma (France), University of Bristol, Saarland University, NANDA TECHNOLOGIES GMBH, INSERM, Cysmic, VHIR, UZH, and IBEC. The page also features navigation links for 'Home', 'Deposit', 'Link', 'Search', 'About', and 'Develop', and a 'Sign in' button.

3. Collaborations: So we want to list all those partners, Aurora universities work together with, using the link between the publications and the projects. And if we have that link, we want to filter on a specific SDG, by using the publications as a proxy.